

ISic0729

I.Sicily inscription 0729

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.01.16

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Lucia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo

Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 43023

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

1. d A(ulo) Tedio A(uli) f(ilio) A[ugurino][---]

2. (vac.undefined) praefec[to---]

3. [---]Ti(berius) u[---]

Apparatus

Text based on Manganaro 1989

The last two visible letters at the beginning of the nomen are either 'Qu-' or 'Ov-'.

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175783

EDCS 6100283

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0342h

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 53

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 183 no.65

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